

Using DSpice for Simulating a Van Der Pol Oscillator

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Abstract:

The Van Der Pol oscillator is a classical non-linear oscillator with applications spanning various scientific and engineering disciplines. Characterized by its self-sustaining oscillations, it serves as a foundational model in studying non-linear dynamics and chaos theory. This document outlines the principles of the Van Der Pol oscillator and provides a detailed method for simulating it using DSpice (Designing Circuits and Simulation by SPICE “Simulation Program with Integrated Circuit Emphasis”). The simulation involves constructing an equivalent electronic circuit that mimics the differential equation governing the oscillator's behavior, leveraging DSpice's capabilities to analyse and visualize the resulting oscillatory patterns.

Keywords: Ngspice, DSpice, Circuits, CAD, oscillator , python, Van Der Pol

I. Introduction

New The Van Der Pol oscillator, named after the Dutch engineer Balthasar Van der Pol, is a fundamental model in non-linear dynamics, originally formulated in the 1920s [1]. The oscillator is defined by a second-order differential equation:

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} - \mu(1-x^2)\frac{dx}{dt} + x = 0 \quad (1)$$

where:

- x represents the system's state (such as voltage in an electronic circuit).
- μ is a parameter indicating the nonlinearity and strength of damping.

For positive values of μ , the system exhibits non-linear damping, providing energy for small oscillations and dissipating energy for large oscillations, leading to self-sustained limit cycles. The Van Der Pol oscillator is used to model a variety of phenomena, from electrical circuits to biological rhythms like heartbeats.

II. Simulating the Van Der Pol Oscillator Using DSpice

DSpice [2][3] is a powerful tool for simulating electronic circuits, widely used in both academia and industry. To simulate the Van Der Pol oscillator using DSpice, we need to create an equivalent electronic circuit that captures the behavior described by the differential equation.

Fig. 1 The interface graphic of DSpice

a. Circuit design

The Fig .2 is equivalent circuit for the Van Der Pol oscillator typically includes:

- An inductor (L1)
- A capacitor (C1)
- A nonlinear resistor, which can be implemented using a voltage-controlled current source to introduce the required nonlinearity.

Fig. 2 The equivalent circuit for the Van Der Pol oscillator by DSpice

(b) Component explanation

- **L1 (1H,-6A):** An inductor with a value of 1 Henry with initial current -6A .
- **C1 (1F,2V):** A capacitor with a value of 1 microFarad and initial voltage 2V.
- **R1 ({1/(V(Out)*V(Out)-1)}):** A resistor with a nonlinear value set the time scale of the oscillator with voltage-controlled current source implementing the non-linear damping term $\mu(1-x^2)$ for $\mu=1$.

The equation in circuit:

$$i_C + i_R + i_L = 0 \quad (2)$$

By replace i_C , i_R and i_L by voltage:

$$C \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{R} V + \frac{1}{L} \int V \partial t = 0 \quad (3)$$

By derivative equation (3) we obtained ven der pol equation:

$$C \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{L} V = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where:

$$C = 1, L = 1 \text{ and } R = -\frac{1}{\mu(1-V^2)} = \frac{1}{\mu(V^2 - 1)}$$

$$V = V(\text{out})$$

Result of simulation as shown in Fig. 3. [4]. Relaxation oscillation in the Van der Pol oscillator without external forcing. The nonlinear damping parameter is equal to $\mu = 1$.

Fig. 3 The result of simulation

III. Conclusion

The Van Der Pol oscillator represents a fundamental example of a non-linear dynamical system, characterized by self-sustained oscillations and limit cycles. Its mathematical formulation and diverse applications make it a vital model in both theoretical studies and practical implementations across various scientific and engineering fields.

Simulating the Van Der Pol oscillator using DSpice provides valuable insights into its dynamic behavior. By constructing an equivalent electronic circuit, we can explore how the system responds to different parameters and initial conditions. The DSpice simulation illustrates the non-linear damping effects and the resulting sustained oscillations, demonstrating the oscillator's unique properties.

Through this simulation, we gain a deeper understanding of non-linear systems and their applications. The ability to model and analyze such systems with DSpice is a powerful tool, allowing researchers and engineers to design and test circuits and

systems that exhibit complex dynamical behavior. By adjusting parameters like the nonlinearity coefficient (μ) and component values, we can tailor the oscillator's behavior to meet specific requirements, making the Van Der Pol oscillator a versatile and practical model in non-linear dynamics.

References

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